

Visual computing and Radar tools for improved situational awareness in Search and Rescue operations

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The Project

The **RESCUER** project is focused on designing and developing a First-Responder-centered technology toolkit, through the “HERO” (enHanced nEW eRa first respOnder) concept.

RESCUER tools and systems will allow for faster positioning of FRs as well as faster localisation of victims and improved operational efficiency of FRs.

The Consortium

20 partners from:

- Spain
- Italy
- France
- Greece
- Germany
- United Kingdom
- Portugal
- Slovakia
- Austria

9 research institutes

6 end-users

3 SMEs

1 large enterprise

1 ICT company

The Goal

RESCUER aims:

- to create and develop a technology toolkit with a First Responder focus.
- equip the upcoming group of first responders.
- enhancing the effectiveness and safety of their operations.
- especially under tough circumstances.
- both in terms of infrastructure and the environment.

“HERO” (enHanced nEw eRa first respOnder) concept, will deliver a toolkit offering:

1. Sense augmentation
2. Precise and infrastructure-less self-positioning
3. Cognitive support and multi-sense AR interfaces
4. Robust ad-hoc intra-team communications for both verbal and data exchanges

The Roadmap

Duration: 36 months
(July 2021 – June 2024)

- Three phases
 - Initial development
 - Core development
 - Maturation Phase

Phase I:

- Use Case Tools' Requirements & Scenarios
- Tools' Architecture & Module Specification
- Technology Research
- Preliminary Modules & Tools Development

Phase II:

- Technology Integration
- 1st Version of RESCUER Edge Tools
- Technical Validation, Testing & Optimization
- Usability & Performance Analysis
- 1st Pilots

Phase III:

- Pilot & First Responders Feedback
- Final Versions of RESCUER Edge Tools
- Technical Validation, Testing & Optimization
- Usability & Performance Analysis
- Final Pilots
- First Responder Feedback & Policy Recommendations

Start

Year 1

Year 2

End

The Tools

Three pillars

- Infrastructure based communication
- Ad-hoc communication
- Internal Communication

Protocol colors

- 3G/4G
- Bluetooth
- WiFi
- Zigbee/Zwave
- Wired

Internal communication
(personal FR devices)

Ad-Hoc communication
(between team members)

Ad-Hoc communication
(between team members)

Radar sensing

This tool perform scene analysis of the individual FR's surroundings

- FMCW-type radar
- location prediction
- object identification
- target tracking
- alerts the first responder

Signs of life detection

This tool will detect if a victim is behind walls or obstacles

- microwave radar sensor (X band 8-10 GHz)
- victim detection behind walls
- victim health status (breathing or not)
- lightweight
- low-cost solution
- accurate results

Robust Vision

This tool is a pipeline of two different sub-tools:

- image denoising
 - DW-GAN network
 - Scans 2D images and removes noise and haze e.g. smoke
 - Excellent performance in non-homogeneous cases
 - Produce a clear image
- object detection
 - Receives the clear image from the image denoising tool
 - Processed by YOLOv4 algorithm
 - Produce images with detection of people and objectives

First row: hazy images & YOLOv4

Second row: results of CERH's model & YOLOv4.

Third row: results of DW-GAN model & YOLOv4

Indoor visual localization

This tool provides the location of the FR

- uses 360 panoramic images
- 3D building/room model
- perform a virtual camera snap(yellow dots)
- produce a combined snap from inputted data
- provides the exact location of the rescuer in the room

Pilots overview

- Two pilot cycles
 - 1st pilot after the 1st version of the tools
 - 2nd pilot after the final tool versions

Country	Scenario	1 st PILOT	2 nd PILOT
GERMANY	Earthquake	November 2022	April 2024
FRANCE	Tunnel fire	March 2023	May 2024
SPAIN	Mountain rescue	January 2023	March 2024

- Field trials during tool development

- Before pilots for several testings
- Already executed in:
 - Greece
 - Germany
 - Spain

- 1st pilot cycle goal

- Technical verification and validation
- Requirements will be re-targeted to address the end-user needs

- 2nd pilot cycle goal

- Refined results and feedback
- Final version of tools

The execution of this phase will be formulated as **policy outcomes and a set of recommendations.**

Field trial in Greece

- Old mine of Vavdos, Chalkidiki
- 18th of June 2022
- Technical partners and End-users
 - Urban Search & Rescue Department of Hellenic Rescue Team(HRT)
 - Center for Research & Technology Hellas(CERTH)
 - University of West Attica
- Earthquake scenario
 - INSARAG 2020 Guidelines, Volume 2: Preparedness and Response's
- First in-field testings

Trial testing

Radar sensing and robust vision tests in harsh (heavy to light smoke) conditions

Trial testing

Indoor visual localization tool tests

Radar sensing tool tests

Trial results

The Signs of life detection tool

Trial results

The radar sensing tool

Trial results

The indoor visual localization tool

3D model of the building

360 image input from FR's location

Rendered view inside the point cloud

Trial results

The Robust vision tool

Object detection in smoke: without dehazing pre-processing

Object detection in smoke: with dehazing pre-processing

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